

FRACTURE BEHAVIOR OF CARBON FIBER REINFORCED POLYPROPYLENE UNDER ARTIFICIAL LIGHTNING STRIKE

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1. Introduction

CFRP (carbon fiber reinforced plastics) has been used for many kinds of structures such as aerospace and sporting goods because of its superior mechanical properties. In recent years, the application to automotive structures is also considered in order to reduce energy consumption in transport sector, but it has not been realized yet because of its high cost, low productivity and low recyclability. However, novel CFRTPs (carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastics) for mass production automobile was developed in Japanese METI-NEDO project (2008-2012fy) to solve these problems [1]. These CFRTPs show not only high mechanical properties, high cycle moldability, high recyclability, but also excellent energy absorption capacity. This ductility is caused because these CFRTPs are difficult to

delaminate. For these superior properties, CFRTPs are expected as suitable material for automobile structures, but many properties are not revealed yet because it is a new material the matrix of which is polypropylene. In order to apply CFRTPs to automobile structures, it is necessary to reveal many kinds of properties and to secure reliability. To achieve this goal, understanding functional properties such as heat and fire resistance, as well as mechanical properties is essential. Especially, securing the safety of passengers is important among these functional properties, so the examination about crash safety and lightning safety has to be done immediately.

Unlike metal materials including steel and aluminum which have been widely used for automobile structures, CFRP has electrical anisotropy caused by the orientation of the carbon fiber, so CFRP is estimated to be complicatedly damaged by lightning

strike. Concerning the fracture behavior of CF/EP (carbon fiber reinforced epoxy) under lightning strike, Hirano et al. [2] examined the detail of it. They added an artificial lightning to CF/EP specimen which has no structure for lightning resistance, observed the damage behavior and considered a relationship between lightning parameter and break of the surface fiber, resin deterioration, and delamination. Feraboli and Miller [3] also performed an artificial lightning strike experiment and examined damage resistance and tolerance of CF/EP coupons with and without fastener. Kawakami and Feraboli [4] examined the resistance and tolerance of copper mesh-protected CF/EP specimen by flexural tests after scarf repair and considered the difference of the fracture behavior under artificial lightning strike caused by the existence of electrical continuity around an area of scarf repair. Not only these experimental studies but also some analytical studies were performed [5]-[8] such as the coupled thermal-electrical analysis by Ogasawara et al. [8]. About lightning strike, a lot of studies were performed [9]-[11] as well as these studies and all these studies were about CFRTPs (carbon fiber reinforced thermoset resins) used for aerospace structure. In addition, an effective solution was proposed about practical lightning protection system for composite structures [12]. On the other hand, a study about lightning protection of CFRTPs for mass production automobile has not been performed yet. Considering about mass production of automobile, conventional lightning protection system, such as copper mesh, cannot be applied, so a new measure for lightning protection must be required. Hence at first, it is necessary to reveal the fracture behavior of CFRTPs systematically.

In this study, we focused on the fracture behavior of CFRTPs under lightning strike developed in the

Japanese national project. The objective of this study is to reveal the fundamental fracture mechanism and whether delamination which causes fatal deterioration of mechanical properties occurs or not after lightning strike. Artificial lightning strike tests of laboratory scale were performed by using CMT (carbon fiber mat reinforced thermoplastics) as the specimen. In the test procedure, we performed not only photography of the damage generation process with high speed camera and the observation of damage area by optical microscope but also tests with changing the parameter of artificial lightning strike and quantitative evaluation of the relationship between damage area and parameter of impulse current in order to reveal the fundamental fracture behavior. In addition, about CFRTPs which are difficult to delaminate against mechanical impact, we investigated whether the mechanism was also effective for electrical impact or not.

2. Experimental Method

2.1 Materials

CMT (carbon fiber mat reinforced thermoplastics) which is shown in Fig. 1 was used as the test specimen. In CMT material, short carbon fiber is randomly dispersed in plane, so the material shows quasi-isotropic. The length of the carbon fiber is about 6 mm. The V_f (volume fraction) of CMT is 30 % or 20 % and the matrix is polypropylene. This material was developed for mass production automobile and provided by Toray Industries, Inc. We considered that the effects of thickness and size of specimen was negligible in the test condition of this study, so the thickness was fixed to 0.8 mm ($V_f = 30\%$) and 1.1mm ($V_f = 20\%$).

2.2 Artificial lightning strike experiment

Impulse current generator was used for adding artificial lightning strike to CMT specimen. The discharge mechanism of spot welder was applied to this equipment. Spot welder is the equipment that electrical energy is discharged through contact surface of matrix and joint part is heated intensively by arc heat for jointing. By using this mechanism, variable electric charge (voltage and capacity are

variable) is added to CMT specimen and damage under lightning strike can be generated artificially. The experimental procedures are as follows. CMT specimen the size of which was 110 mm × 110 mm was set on the supporting jig as shown in Fig. 2 and one connected cable to the spot welder was connected to this supporting jig. A wire with the diameter of 0.8 mm was set as a discharge probe at the tip of the other cable and was attached to the height variable part of height gauge. Then, we set the capacity of condenser and the voltage, charged the condenser in spot welder, and let a probe descend slowly with the adjustment screw of the height gauge. Hence we can evaluate without any effects, such as potential energy, other than artificial lightning strike. When the discharge probe came close to specimen enough, an electric discharge occurred and damage was generated on the specimen. The procedures mentioned above were repeated four times for each condition. The testing condition is shown in Table. 1.

In addition, photography with high speed camera was performed in the artificial lightning test in order to observe the generation behavior of damage. Photron FASTCAM SA-X was used and the shutter speed was from 30,000frame/s to 50,000frame/s. Moreover, in order to confirm that the test equipment used in this study simulates an actual lightning strike enough, measurement of lightning current waveform was performed with Rogowski coil. Rogowski coil is generally used for the measurement of lightning current in wind turbine, skyscraper and so on [13][14]. In this study, we refer to the Rogowski coil which Yasumoto et al. [15] used in the Mt. Fuji weather station. First, enameled wire was wound forty times around three wooden rings to make Rogowski coil. Circuit of the measurement system was shown in Fig. 4. This circuit takes the output voltage and integrates it. The output voltage is as follows:

$$e_2 = \frac{1}{20R_1C} \int \left(M \frac{di}{dt} \right) dt = \frac{M}{20R_1C} \cdot i \quad (1)$$

where M is the mutual inductance between cable and the Rogowski coil, and equal to 0.14 μ H, R_1 is the input resistance of integral calculus circuit, and equal to 10 k Ω , and C is the capacity of integral

calculus condenser and equal to 2 nF. The output voltage per unit of electric current of measured cable is calculated to 0.35 mV/A by substituting these design values to Eq. (1). The condenser parallel resistance of the integral calculus circuit was set to 10 M Ω , so a slow phenomenon of 20 ms degree was measurable. A coaxial cable with the characteristic impedance of 50 Ω was used for transmission channel, and the output impedance of detector side amplifier and of the integral calculus circuit of measurement part was set to 50 Ω in order to make them match to the impedance of the coaxial cable. The output voltage of Rogowski coil is the derivative of the electric current which flows through the cable. Then, the voltage in proportion to the electric current flowing through the cable can be provided by putting the output voltage of Rogowski coil through the integral calculus circuit.

3. Experimental Results and Discussion

3.1 Measurement of current waveform

In order to confirm that the test equipment used in this study simulates an actual lightning strike enough, measurement of lightning current waveform was performed with Rogowski coil. The typical result is shown in Fig. 5. As a result, T_1/T_2 was 50/300 μ s in condition “J” and 45/270 μ s in condition “E”. Where, T_1 [μ s] and T_2 [μ s] are, respectively, the time from 10% to 90% of the maximum current and the time from 10% to 50% through 90% of the maximum current. These results did not completely agree with the waveform which was standardized by JIS Z 9290-4 [16], but it was found that this equipment was generally able to simulate an actual lightning phenomenon. The peak current was about 1.2 kA in condition “J”, so this test was about a one-100th scale. By the way, it was difficult to produce an accurate waveform because of the limitation of the testing equipment and we made a scale of this artificial lightning test small in order to obtain more data with small specimen, so the waveform which was different from the waveform determined by a standard was applied in this study.

3.2 Observation of external damage

The damages of CMT after artificial lightning were observed by optical microscope, VHX-1000 made by KEYENCE. The picture of damage in condition “I” is shown in Fig. 6 as a typical result of damage caused by artificial lightning strike. Damages can be divided into three parts, and the damage generation behavior was the same in all condition. The shape of damage was almost circle shape and it can be said that it reflected isotropic of CMT in plane direction. The dented area occurred at nearest part of lightning point. This area is shown in Fig. 6 by continuous line. By performing the photography with high speed camera, it was found that strong white light emission which covered the whole screen of the camera occurred at the same time as the generation of spark. Therefore, it was estimated that carbon fiber burned up in this area. From now, this area is called “fiber burned area”.

A swelled part was generated around the fiber burned area. This area is shown by a broken line in Fig. 6 and looks particularly black. By the photography with high speed camera, it was found that, following the strong white light emission by combustion of carbon fiber, orange flame appeared and intense heat was generated around the part of lightning point (Fig. 7). It is estimated that the orange flame caught fire in polypropylene vaporized by the intensive heat. In addition, polypropylene around the near part of lightning point was melted and flowed to the surrounding area. The flowed polypropylene was gradually cooled and became solid when it became under the melting temperature. This resin generated the swelled area. From now, this area is called “resin melted area” and it includes the fiber burned area.

An area the surface fiber of which stood out slightly was widely distributed around the resin melted area. This corresponds to the outside of broken line in Fig. 6, but the whole part of this area is not seen in this figure. In Fig. 9, the left picture shows the behavior before the artificial lightning strike and the right one is about after the artificial lightning strike. By comparison of both pictures, it was clearly found that carbon fiber surrounding the part of artificial lightning point stood out. CMT material is made by press molding of carbon fiber mat and resin film, so it was estimated that surface resin softened in heat and it came to be impossible to press down the

carbon fiber mat. Also, it could be estimated that this area was heat affected zone which was caused by heat transfer in plane direction and by radiant heat generated by the combustion of vaporized polypropylene. From now, this area is called “heat affected zone” and it includes the fiber burned area and the resin melted area mentioned above.

These damages accompanied by burning up of carbon fiber and heating of resin, so they may influence the mechanical properties of structure. In the fiber burned area, it is clear that the amount of carbon fiber was reduced and V_f decreased. In addition, about the resin melted area and the heat affected zone, the influence by heating and melting is concerned. Hence the properties of the resin in heat affected area may change, so the evaluation of mechanical properties after lightning strike is one of the important problems in the future.

3.3 Observation of internal damage

In order to observe each damage area in more detail and to evaluate whether delamination which leads to fatal deterioration of mechanical properties occurred or not, X-ray imaging was performed with three-dimensional X-rays CT device made by Yamato Scientific Co., Ltd.

Fig. 10 shows CF/EP uni-directional specimen after artificial lightning strike in condition “J”, and break of surface fiber and delamination in some surface layers were observed. It was shown in many references such as [2] and [3].

On the other hand, in CMT material, there was no delamination as shown in Fig. 11, only some bulge like spring back in molding process was observed. As a result, it was confirmed that the property of CFRTP which was difficult to delaminate was also effective to electrical impact as well as mechanical impact. Therefore, from the viewpoint of structural integrity, CFRTPs have superior property that delamination which causes fatal deterioration of energy absorption property does not occur after lightning strike.

3.4 Relationship between the parameter of impulse current and damage area

The objective of this section is to evaluate the relationship between the degree of damages and some parameters of artificial lightning strike. In this

study, we focused on the energy charged in the condenser of impulse current generator and the total amount of electric charge. Transient phenomena which occurs in very short time is quite complex, but the evaluation was performed by assuming that all electrical energy and electric charge were discharged to specimen. In addition, the three areas mentioned in section 3.2 were evaluated as damage areas. These evaluation was performed by the optical microscope VHX-1000 made by KEYENCE. The results of all condition are shown in Fig. 12, Fig. 13, and Fig. 14. It was found that the area of fiber burned area, resin melted area, and heat affected zone has strong relationship with added heat, that is, electrical energy charged in condenser. Also, as shown in Fig. 15, Fig. 16, and Fig. 17, it is clear that each damage area has strong correlation with heat energy, not electrical charge. As a result, it can be said that fiber burned area and resin melted area are established by joule heat caused by the applied impulse current. Therefore, it is estimated that a series of damage generation does not depend on a kind of resin, in case of CMT the matrix of which is thermoplastics.

In case of CMT with V_f of 30%, the area of heat affected zone was not so different from that with V_f of 20%, but the fiber damaged area and resin melted area were smaller. It may be caused by the difference of electrical conductivity of two materials. Table. 2 shows the measurement results of electrical conductivity of two materials by two terminals method with silver paste. In case of lower σ_x , electrical conductivity in plane direction, the large heat generation does not diffuse and concentrates, so the amount of carbon fiber burning and resin melting become large. In addition, in case of higher σ_x , heat generation does not concentrate and heat is widely transferred in plane direction, so heat affected zone is expected to be larger, but in case of CMT whose V_f is 30%, σ_z , electrical conductivity of thickness direction, is high as well as σ_x , so it is estimated that electric current which flows into thickness direction was also high. In this case, the amount of electric current which flows into thickness direction might not be large as the damage progresses to thickness direction, because σ_z is much lower than σ_x . This fact was also indicated by Todoroki [17]. That is, in case that σ_z is much lower than σ_x , most of electric current flows through the surface of

specimen by skin effect. In fact, as shown in Fig. 11, the dent to the thickness direction was so small and there was no damage which reached to the back face of CMT specimen in the range of artificial lightning test in this study.

4. Conclusions

In this study, impulse current generator was made and artificial lightning test was performed to reveal the fundamental fracture behavior of CFRTPs for mass production automobile. In addition, these tests were performed with changing the parameter of artificial lightning and the effects of lightning parameter on the degree of damage were evaluated. Also, in order to observe the phenomenon during lightning strike, photography by high speed camera was performed. The conclusions of this study are shown as following.

- Damages of CMT under lightning strike are divided into three areas, that is, fiber burned area, resin melted area, and heat affected zone. At the same time as lightning strike, strong white light was generated, so it is estimated that the temperature of the part of lightning strike point rapidly rose in very short time and that fiber burning occurred. Then, orange flame was generated and it may be caused by the combustion of vaporized polypropylene. In addition, by photography of high speed camera, the main factor of the generation of resin melted area can be estimated that resin melted by heat was flown into the circumference of the lightning strike point, was cooled and became solid. Also, the main factor of generation of heat affected zone can be estimated to be the heat transfer caused by a series of the lightning strike process and to be the radiant heat caused by the generated flame.
- The area of fiber burned area, resin melted area, and heat affected zone had a strong relationship with heat energy added to specimen. As a result, it can be said that the carbon fiber burning in central area and the swelled area of melted resin around the fiber burned area were caused by joule heat generated by impulse current. Therefore, it is estimated that a series of damage generation process does not depend on

the kind of resin, in case that the matrix is thermoplastics.

- There is high possibility that each damage generated under lightning strike causes some deterioration of mechanical properties, but unlike CF/EP, there was no delamination in CMT material, so it is said that the behavior is desirable from the viewpoint of structural integrity. In addition, the ease of repairing by thermoplasticity is expected to be an advantage of this material.

CMT material
($V_f = 30\%$, 20%)

Fig. 1 Illustration of CF/PP CMT.

Fig. 2 Supporting jig and specimen setup.

Fig. 3 Supporting jig (side view).

Fig. 4 Illustration of circuit of the impulse testing equipment.

Fig. 5 Impulse waveform (condition "J").

Fig. 6 Fracture behavior of CMT under artificial lightning strike. (condition "I")

Fig. 7 Combustion of gasified PP.

Fig. 8 Generation of resin melted area.

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Fig. 9 Specimen surface before and after lightning strike.
(left: before, right: after)

Fig. 10 Sectional view of CF/EP specimen by X-ray imaging. (condition "J", $t=1.6\text{mm}$)

Fig. 11 Sectional view of CMT specimen by X-ray imaging. (condition J, $t=1.1\text{mm}$)

Fig. 12 Relationship between fiber burned area and joule heat.

Fig. 13 Relationship between resin melted area and joule heat.

Fig. 14 Relationship between heat affected zone and joule heat.

Fig. 15 Comparison of fiber burned area.

Fig. 16 Comparison of resin melted area.

Fig. 17 Comparison of heat affected zone.

Table 1 Testing conditions for artificial lightning test.

Condition	Voltage [V]	Condenser capacity [μ F]	Joule heat [J]	Electrical charge [C]
A	400	200	16	0.08
B	400	400	32	0.16
C	400	600	48	0.24
D	400	800	64	0.32
E	400	1,000	80	0.40
F	400	1,200	96	0.48
G	400	1,400	112	0.56
H	400	1,600	128	0.64
I	400	1,800	144	0.72
J	400	2,000	160	0.80
a	200	800	16	0.16
b	200	1,600	32	0.32

Table 2 Electrical conductivities of CMT.

	V_f [%]	In-plane direction conductivity	Thickness direction conductivity
		σ_x [S/m]	σ_z [S/m]
CMT	30	6,600	8.5
CMT	20	3,900	5.2

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